

ENGLISH FOR BUSINESS PURPOSES: AN ESP APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15479004>

Annotation

With modern advancements and English becoming an international language there is a huge demand for learning English specifically in business context. In the following article we will discuss ESP (English for specific purposes) focusing on business communication. ESP is a great tool to assist professionals in developing their basic soft skills in the face of job capabilities in business. The article repeats the key aspects of language in the field of business English and describes the famous points of making errors while compiling business speeches or conversation in English.

Key words: Business English, ESP, international business communication, language training.

Topic relevance

Today, English is the basis for jobs such as business, marketing and commerce. For many professionals, entrepreneurs and employees, English language skills in a professional environment have become an integral part of their work and a mandatory requirement for employment in international companies. The ability to build business speech and correspondence in English without barriers, knowledge of how to manage application databases in English will significantly increase your professional level in the eyes of the employer. But the problem is that many

specialists, having received basic education, face a lack of knowledge in ESP (English for Specific Purposes).

English is already used in international trade, which automatically follows a clash between native and non-native speakers of English. Both parties need to be trained to competently build skills such as:

- making presentations
- negotiation
- meeting participation
- business correspondence
- report writing, etc.

The ESP course teaches all the details for mastering the above skills and also points out all sorts of peculiarities in constructing sentence structure in business speech.

Literature Review

The topic of ESP and business communication was considered thirty years ago, the writers Tom Hutchinson and Alan Waters in 1987 published a book «English for Specific Purposes», where they detailed the importance of ESP courses and explained how to work with them. The book will be a good guide to delving into the subject of ESP if you are a beginner, and for more experienced readers it will serve as an incentive to learn something new.

The book «Developments in English for Specific Purposes» by Dudley-Evans and St John takes a deeper look at the subject of ESPs, categorising them into specific areas of work, highlighting the differences of each one.

An equally essential book for understanding the basics and principles of ESP courses: «Developing Courses in English for Specific Purposes», written by H. Basturkmen, tells the story of the development of ESP by teachers, touching on experimental experiences.

Problems and solutions

One of the main problems when starting to learn English is the almost complete lack of live practice. Teachers usually emphasize vocabulary and grammar, which makes it very difficult to become fluent in English. For business speech in English the situation is even more difficult, with little emphasis on the specifics of correct business speech and no interest in real business situations.

The second major challenge is the difficulty in customizing ESP training for different industries. As we have already learnt, the ESP is a set of all the terms and structures necessary for doing business. However, this includes too many industries, so there is a problem of lack of teachers.

The following ways are suggested to address these challenges:

- Designing ESP courses to meet specific professional requirements, which will lead to spreading interest and attracting professionals into the field of ESP training.
- The use of actual materials: business documents, negotiation notes, real letters and reports.
- Introduction of a practical approach: role-playing, simulations of business meetings, etc.
- Active use of modern technologies, such as online platforms, virtual meeting rooms, business simulations.

These problems exist in a global learning environment, but when you are already studying on an ESP course, you face very different challenges. In business speech, some aspects are important that we are used to ignoring in ordinary life.

For example:

1. When agreeing on a meeting, it is crucial to clarify the time and place of the meeting and inform your business partner.
2. At various corporate conferences, show interest, freely express your point of view.
3. If you do not understand the goals or objectives set before you, be sure to ask clarifying questions.
4. Do not forget about feedback for your colleagues, point out both mistakes and excellent work and accept criticism with understanding.
5. When you have finished your presentation, remember to thank the audience for their time.

Scientifically based suggestions and recommendations

Based on the analysis of the current level of ESP and current educational opportunities, the following recommendations can be proposed:

- Introduction of ESP courses into higher education programs. Universities should introduce specialized ESP courses taking into account the most demanded professions.
- Upgrading the skills of existing employees. Companies can introduce ESP programs to improve the professional level of the team.
- Use of hybrid methods of training. Nowadays it is possible to schedule both offline and online meetings, which will make it much easier to learn ESP courses.

- Creating special training programs. To make the learning process as effective as possible, it is necessary to adapt to the personal needs of learners, adapting the materials to their professional sphere.
- Using artificial intelligence and digital technology. To make the work of teachers easier, AI tools can analyze students' mistakes and offer individual recommendations to each one.

These suggestions will help improve the quality of ESP teaching and increase the level of business English proficiency among professionals.

Conclusion

In today's era where global markets are actively interacting, professionals with ESP proficiency are critical to their career achievements. ESP extends the possibilities of personalized linguistic education, significantly increasing success. Learning ESP (English for Specific Purposes) improves workplace skills such as negotiation, business correspondence, report writing and idea sharing, making workers better at their jobs. By funding into the development of their employees in ESP, firms benefit in global co-operation, market expansion and improved customer service. Thus, ESP people are very important and necessary in the success of a company these days. Global, technical progress as well as the strengthening of co-operation on an international level require skilled, career-oriented English language skills, confirming the importance of ESP in commerce.

References

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